

On the nature of truth in the interdimensional hypothesis

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Abstract

The relativistic nature of the universe, as well as questions regarding the existence of absolute truth, still pose an impasse in Philosophy of science, what is true for some is false for others; what is at rest for some is in motion for others. Everything in the universe is a matter of relativity. Thus, this article presents the interdimensional hypothesis, a new approach to address the problem of the absolute or relative nature of truth in the universe, which may help us rethink the way we are used to see the reality and up bring relevant new ideas with strong philosophical implications.

1 Motivation

The development of the interdimensional hypothesis, was motivated by the need of finding a general laws that governs the truths in the universe, this was due to my appreciation of the unreasonable effectiveness of mathematics in the description of the real structure of everything, by means of mathematics I could understand that everything in the nature has pattern, every objects has a structure and every phenomenon follows a trend, however, I noticed that we have set a limit on what mathematics can be applied, for us mathematics is only applied to study the physical world or even events at the microscopical levels with the apparent implications, but what if mathematics also suggests that everything, seen or unseen, abstract or tangible can also hold a law ? what if there is as well a hidden pattern or law that govern the world of ideas and the way the truth is identified and perceived ? is exactly what this hypothesis comes for, to propose that if we can not perceive things with absolute certainty, then there must be a law that governs this philosophical paradigm. Is exactly this that motivates the birth of the interdimensional treatment for the truth.

2 Two different settings for the truth

Our daily life experiences has shown us the existence of two different settings regarding to the nature of truth, the absolute and the relative settings, the

exact definition of the truth in these settings often appears contradictory, for example regarding to the concepts of time, there was a conflict between its nature, Albert Einstein for example defended that the concept of time is a relative truth, while Isaac Newton believed in the existence of an absolute time, and since the relativistic character of time is seen from the first principles we have adopted it as the true version of time, however, this relativistic nature of time is only perceived when we compare between inertial frames. such that if any comparison is being performed, the concept of relative time does not make sense at all, this proves that the truth may exist in two different realms, an absolute and a relative setting, on the other hand, the existence of mathematics also poses a strong evidence of the existence of a universe far from ours where everything agree with each other, there is not contradiction in the world of mathematics, all set of consistent ideas, theorems and axioms form a unique and coherent system without discrepancies, hence from this we can convince ourselves that the absolute settings exists independently of comparisons and in this settings the truth about an object is independent to the way we may represent it, the truth there is unique, well defined.

Thus, from this analogies is important to acknowledge that when trying to find out the truth about something or when discussing if either something is true or false, we must first check the settings we are based on our analysis, since no everything that make sense in the relative settings may also make sense in an absolute point of view. Therefore, the absolute and relative settings do not contradict each other, instead the lack of awareness of their existences is what disrupt our exploration in the pursuit of the truth, such that the relative and absolute truths are just different parts of an infinite universe.

3 The interdimensional hypothesis

In this hypothesis, it is assumed that in a universe there are multiple dimensions, each with its own characteristics, where a certain element acquires new aspects. Therefore, the composition of the laws of each dimension constitutes the peculiarities of the elements in that universe, so that a given element.

Thus, the composition of the laws of each dimension constitutes the peculiarities of the elements in such a universe. For this purpose, a given element in the universe in question will be the result of the relationships between dimensions, that is, the element will carry within itself an interdimensionality, and may, from the same perspective, be equivalent to itself and not be so from different perspectives.

However, everything in a universe has a pattern, and every pattern is linked to a dimension, whose relationship with others reflects the concept of interdimensionality, making things equivalent or not equivalent to themselves.

In this line of reasoning, the interdimensional hypothesis unravel a new aspect of the reality, that lies crucially on the relationships between the interdimensional field and the one-dimensional field, hence explaining the phenomenon of relativism and absolutism. From this, we can deduce that relativism is the property that governs all elements in an interdimensional field, while absolutism governs the elements in a one-dimensional field.

The relationship of the interdimensional field is what explains the relativistic character, expressing for this purpose the reason for relativism, so all universes that were formed on the basis of the interdimensional field are designated “relative universes,” as is the case with our universe, which is why it is said that it is impossible for us to know the absolute truth, even though it only exists in one-dimensional fields (absolute universe).

Additionally, the unreasonable effectiveness of mathematics has shown us that the universe is mathematical, such that even the truth can be considered a mathematical object, this may appear as little surprising since the common sense has led us to believe that the truth is only an object of philosophy so that it is senseless claim the existence of a general mathematical formula or pattern to explain the truth, it may even appear as paradoxical since mathematics itself aims at achieving the truth. Thus, in some sense the interdimensional hypothesis may be considered as a paradox as it dictates the possibility of know the truth by means of a truth, however, we know already from the Godel incompleteness theorem that any consistent logical system cannot prove its own consistency, this suggests that even though we may find the first principle for the truth, this principle can not prove that is consistent inside its logical system so that it will be needed others systems logically consistent to serve as basis for a proof.

Therefore, the interdimensional hypothesis uses the Godel incompleteness theorem to find out the first principles which governs the nature of truth in a given universe, as this principle can not be proved or stated by its own.

Mathematically, the interdimensional hypothesis resumes into the following:

There exists a mathematical structure in which identity and difference co-exist, such that any two identities A and B can be simultaneously equal and unequal, provided that these truths exists in different dimensions A and B, such that :

$$\forall A, B \in U, A \equiv B \iff \exists (d_1, d_2) \in D^n | A|d_1 = B|d_1 \wedge A|d_2 \neq B|d_2$$

The proposition stated below has not yet a proof, since the conjecture is still under conceptual development and the goal of this essay is to present a glimpse into the interdimensional realm of truth. The mathematical statement is slightly trivial since it is self evidence to the context we are analyzing, additionally, it encodes the mathematical form of the interdimensional and the one-dimensional field as stated earlier in this essay, the field we are making reference is not

the same as the classical field studied in Physics or in many areas of pure mathematics, instead by field we mean a particular or singular dimension of a universe, the collection of all of this dimensions is what forms the reality, the world of ideas made of diverse perspectives and points of views.

4 Conclusion

Therefore, the interdimensional hypothesis states that the truth has exactly two nature-the relative and the absolute nature in a universe, which exists in inter-dimensional and one-dimensional fields, these field constitute the characteristics or properties of objects in that universe.